

THE PROBLEMS IN TEACHING YOUNG LEARNERS

Tolipova Billura Ravshanovna
teacher of Andizhan state university
interfaculty of foreign languages

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8001621>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 31th May 2023

Accepted: 31th May 2023

Online: 31th May 2023

KEYWORDS

young learners, immersion, four skills, approaches and methods of teaching young learners, oral and written discourse for young learners, language skillst

ANNOTATION

the given article is aimed to familiarize students with features of teaching young learners and appropriate instructional tools to this age group of learners. In addition, it deals with identifying the core of the immersion teaching and other successful approaches, methods and aids of teaching; to identify basic skills which must be developed in teaching young learners; to use approaches and methods in accordance with the suggested stages and type of activity

Introduction

In studies of immersion language learning, younger children (7-8 years) seem to pay more attention to sound and prosody (the 'music' of an utterance), whereas older children (12-14 years) are more attentive to cues of word order. Children are generally less able to give selective and prolonged attention to features of learning tasks than adults, and are more easily diverted and distracted by other pupils. When faced with talk in the new language, they try to understand it in terms of the grammar and salient cues of their first language and also pay particular attention to items of L2 vocabulary that they are familiar with. These findings will not surprise experienced primary teachers, but they give further empirical support to the idea that teachers can help learners by focusing their attention on useful sources of information in the new language, as also suggested by Bruner's scaffolding studies.

Research methodology

In applied linguistics over the last decades, it has been common to divide language into 'the Four Skills': Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing, and then to add Grammar, Vocabulary and Phonology to them. This division is not as logical as it may seem and has been challenged. Some syllabuses also deal in Topics, Functions and Notions, describing language in terms of how it is used in communication rather than seeing it as a linguistic system or a set of skills. Because children who start learning a foreign language very young may encounter nothing but the spoken language for several years, the customary division into the four skills seems somewhat inappropriate, and an alternative division of language has been attempted.

Discussion

For young learners, spoken language is the medium through which the new language is encountered, understood, practiced and learnt. Rather than oral skills being simply one aspect of learning language, the spoken form in the young learner classroom acts as the prime source and site

of language learning. New language is largely introduced orally, understood orally and aurally, practiced and automatized orally. My solution to the problem of how to divide up oral language learning comes from thinking about how children seek out meanings for themselves in language, and to focus on words and on interaction. For Vygotsky, words label concepts and are an entry point into thinking and networks of meaning. In language teaching terms, the development of words, their meanings and the links between them will be covered under the term Vocabulary.

Interaction will be labeled as Discourse skills, which includes conversational exchanges and longer stretches of talk that Snow's work in first language development has identified. Instead of thinking about children as 'doing Listening and Speaking', we will think about how they learn to interact in the foreign language. Classroom activities can also be seen and analysed as discourse in their own right.

Grammar will be seen as emerging from the space between words and discourse in children's language learning, and as being important in constructing and interpreting meaning accurately. The development of phonology is not considered separately, since children seem to develop native-like accents without specific training through exposure to good models; it will, however, link into the development of spelling and rhyme.

Listening is the language skill which learners usually find the most difficult. This often is because they feel under unnecessary pressure to understand every word. To achieve the aims related to this skill, the teacher plays an important role that is defined in the following steps.

1. It is important to help pupils prepare for the listening task well before they hear the text itself. First of all the teacher must ensure that the pupils understand the language they need to complete the task and are fully aware of exactly what is expected of them. Reassure the pupils that they do not need to understand every word they hear.

2. The next important step is to encourage pupils to anticipate what they are going to hear. In everyday life, the situation, the speaker, and visual clues all help us to decode oral messages. A way to make things a bit easier to the pupils is to present the listening activity within the context of the topic of a teaching unit. This in itself will help pupils to predict what the answers might be. The teacher can help them further by asking questions and using the illustrations to encourage pupils to guess the answers even before they hear the text.

3. During the listening the pupils should be able to concentrate on understanding the message so make sure they are not trying to read, draw, and write at the same time. Always give a second chance to listen to the text to provide a new opportunity to those who were not able to do the task.

4. Finally, when pupils have completed the activity, invite answers from the whole class. Try not to put individual pupils under undue pressure. Rather than confirming whether an answer is correct or not, play the cassette again and allow pupils to listen again for confirmation. You may be given a variety of answers, in which case list them all on the board and play the text again, so that the class can listen and choose the correct one. Even if the pupils all appear to have completed the task successfully, always encourage them to listen to the text once more and check their answers for themselves.

In primary schools two main types of speaking activities are used. The first type, songs, chants, and poems, encourages pupils to mimic the model they hear on the cassette. This helps pupils to master the sounds, rhythms, and intonation of the English language through simple reproduction. The games and pair work activities on the other hand, although always based on a given model, encourage the pupils to begin to manipulate the language by presenting them with a certain amount of choice,

albeit within a fairly controlled situation.

In order for any speaking activity to be successful children need to acknowledge that there is a real reason for asking a question or giving a piece of information. Therefore, make sure the activities you present to the pupils, provide a reason for speaking, whether this is to play a game or to find out real information about friends in the class.

Once the activity begins, make sure that the children are speaking as much English as possible without interfering to correct the mistakes that they will probably make. Try to treat errors casually by praising the utterance and simply repeating it correctly without necessarily highlighting the errors. And finally, always offer praise for effort regardless of the accuracy of the English produced.

Since many pupils at this level are not yet capable either linguistically or intellectually of creating a piece of written text from scratch, it is important that time is spent building up the language they will need and providing a model on which they can then base their own efforts. The writing activities should therefore be based on a parallel text and guide the pupils, using simple cues. These writing activities generally appear towards the end of a unit so that pupils have had plenty of exposure to the language and practice of the main structures and vocabulary they need.

At this stage, the pupils' work will invariably contain mistakes. Again, the teacher should try to be sensitive in his/her correction and not necessarily insist on every error being highlighted. A piece of written work covered in red pen is demoralizing and generally counter-productive. Where possible, encourage pupils to correct their own mistakes as they work. If there is time, encourage pupils to decorate their written work and where feasible display their efforts in the classroom.

Results

Teaching literacy of FL, particularly reading, enables young EL pupils to learn their target language within context, and the basis for both written and spoken language is phonics awareness. Letters-and-sounds modeling can be one of the options for implementing phonics approach at primary schools. Once introduced to the sounds of English, the children will be able to read and speak the words properly and will then be aware of how to spell English lexemes that contain different sounds represented with different letters. Besides, children can read and understand the text using their phonics knowledge.

The LEA (Language Experience activity) can be used with very beginning readers and writers because they only need to dictate the stories orally, and even this can be done collaboratively, bringing together the combined abilities of the entire class. Because it involves stories that are first dictated, the LEA allows children to see a direct link between oral and written language. In essence, it involves "writing to read." Because the children have "composed" the stories themselves, there is a close match between their knowledge or experience and the texts they read.

Reference:

1. Marcos Peñate Cabrera. Teaching the Four Skills in the Primary EFL Classroom. // University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (The Canary Islands, Spain). mpenate [at] dde.ulpgc.es.
2. Lynne Cameron. Teaching Language to Young Learners. 2001. <http://www.tpd.ac.nz/site/tpdl/files/Resources%20-%20documents/General/Reading/Cameron%20Teaching%20lgs%20to%20children%20chap%201.pdf>. Pp.15-19.
3. The Internet TESL Journal, Vol. VIII, No. 12, December 2002. <http://iteslj.org/Techniques/Bazo-FourSkills.html>